

Title: State of Addiction Care Innovation in Scotland

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IDEAS in Addiction Medicine
Innovation, Design, Entrepreneurship, Action & Systems
Hub for Addiction Medicine

In partnership with:

Digital Health & Care
Innovation Centre

Research
Data
Scotland

Funded by:

May 2026

Foreword by IDEAS Hub Directors

This report has been prepared as part of the Scottish Council on Global Affairs (SCGA)–funded project *Scotland’s Role in Global Innovation for Addiction Care: A Systems Approach to Public Health Transformation*. It has been led by the IDEAS in Addiction Medicine St Andrews - Innovation, Design, Entrepreneurship, Action & Systems Hub for Addiction Medicine (IDEAS Hub, n.d.), a unique collaboration between the University of St Andrews Business School and School of Medicine, in partnership with Scotland’s Digital Health and Innovation Centre (DHI) and Research Data Scotland (RDS).

The IDEAS Hub aims to foster meaningful, impact-driven collaboration to advance innovation in addiction care, bringing together people with lived and living experience (LLE), community and third sector organisations, the NHS, government, academia, entrepreneurs, industry, and risk capital providers (including philanthropy), both within Scotland and internationally. It seeks to identify critical gaps in knowledge and practice, co-develop evidence-informed programmes and deliver tangible solutions to real-world challenges.

This report examines the current state of addiction care innovation in Scotland - highlighting existing strengths, identifying key gaps, and setting out how Scotland can best mobilise its strengths and innovation assets to play a leading role in global innovation for addiction care. It has been informed by the IDEAS Hub’s extensive engagement within the field, including a three-day Innovation in Addiction Medicine Summit convening over 50 experts from academia, healthcare, policy, and enterprise to explore systems approaches to addiction care innovation and held in September 2025 at St Andrews.

The report demonstrates that meaningful progress depends on system-wide collaboration, coordinated action and shared purpose and is intended to serve as a foundation for more ambitious, coordinated action across Scotland’s addiction care system.

We hope you find this report valuable and invite you to join us in advancing a more innovative, coordinated, and compassionate system of addiction care in Scotland.

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Context

Addiction remains one of Scotland's most complex and urgent public health challenges. Despite significant policy attention and investment, drug- and alcohol-related deaths remain concerningly high, with over 2000 deaths recorded in 2024 (Scottish Government, 2025a; National Records of Scotland, 2024a; National Records of Scotland, 2024b). Outcomes for people experiencing addiction are poor, inequalities persist, and services continue to operate within fragmented systems that struggle to respond to evolving needs (Miall et al., 2022). Co-occurring health and social care issues, and deep-rooted stigma are placing increasing unsustainable pressure on an already over-stretched system.

Innovation in addiction care matters now more than ever as incremental and fragmented improvements are neither sufficient nor sustainable. Addressing the scale and complexity of the challenge requires new ways of working across policy domains, service delivery structures, data, communities, and lived experience (see also Scottish Government and COSLA, 2026). Scotland has strong foundations that could underpin this shift, including a rich data landscape, a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship, and a scale that enables meaningful collaboration across sectors and places (see Corra Foundation, 2025; Care Inspectorate, 2017; Whoriskey et al., 2025; Association of British HealthTech Industries, n.d.; and Scottish Enterprise, 2025). Effectively harnessing these assets presents a significant opportunity to transform addiction care within Scotland and to inform practice globally.

Approach

This SCGA funded project has engaged stakeholders and supported collaborative mapping of innovation assets in addiction care innovation in Scotland. It has included a stakeholder survey, an analysis of a systems approach to innovation in addiction care in Scotland and its global relevance via a focus-group podcast, and an interactive cross-sector policy workshop, titled *Collaborative Innovation in Scottish Addiction Care*. These activities have harvested collective wisdom and insights into what is and is not currently working in Scotland's addiction care system, and inspired collaborative thinking across organisations and individuals, including:

- University of St Andrews
- Digital Health & Care Innovation Centre (DHI) Scotland
- Research Data Scotland (RDS)
- Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations (SCVO)
- We are With You
- Cranstoun
- Drug Policy Division of Scottish Government
- Office for Life Sciences (OLS)
- Public Health Scotland (PHS)
- National Health Service (NHS) Fife
- Scottish Drugs Forum (SDF)

- Effective Prescribing within Scottish Government
- The Salvation Army Centre for Addiction Services and Research at the University of Stirling
- University of Edinburgh
- University of Dundee
- University of Glasgow School of Health and Wellbeing
- Trinity College Dublin
- University of Texas Southwestern
- Harvard Health Tech Fellow

This report reflects the perspectives of participants engaged through the workshop, survey, and podcast and may not capture the full diversity of frontline or lived experience voices. The analysis is intentionally high-level and is offered as a snapshot within a rapidly evolving policy and service context.

Scotland's Unique Foundations for Leadership in Addiction Care Innovation

Scotland has strong foundations from which to assert its international leadership in addiction care innovation. These include embedded values of compassion and human rights, an entrepreneurial mindset, a high standard of evidence-based practice, extensive datasets, and experience of implementing innovative solutions in real-world environments.

Scotland's innovation landscape reveals four key areas of strength:

- **Mission-oriented and rights-based approach:** The Scottish government has championed a rights-based approach to drug policy. The *National Mission on Drug Deaths* (Scottish Government, 2022; Scottish Government, 2023a; Public Health Scotland, 2024) sets out a strategic vision for supporting those impacted by drug use, explicitly recognising that people who use drugs are entitled to treatment despite persistent stigma. This is reinforced by a *Charter of Rights for People Affected by Substance Abuse* (Health and Social Care Alliance Scotland, 2024), which highlights how rights to housing, right to a private life, right to a healthy environment are central to addressing drug-related harms and require a whole-system approach.
- **Risk reduction leadership:** Scotland is a leader in reducing risks and harm for people who take drugs. It introduced a *National Naloxone¹ Programme*, making overdose reversal medication and knowledge widely available (with an 70% 'reach' to people at risk of opioid overdose) (Scottish Government, 2023b). Police officers and other frontline workers now routinely carry Naloxone. Scotland has also pioneered the UK's first safer drug consumption facility (The Thistle), which opened in Glasgow in January 2025.
- **Data, digital health and real-time surveillance:** *Digital Innovation in Addiction Services* (DigitAS, n.d.) St Andrews is developing cutting-edge overdose

¹ Naloxone is a medicine that can save someone's life by quickly reversing the effects of an overdose.

detection approaches using data, medtech, and implementation driven science, helping to shape the future of addiction treatment and prevention. National and international programmes such as the DHI led *Digital Lifelines Scotland Programme* and the *EU PeacePlus* funded *SUMIT project (2025-2028)* are advancing digital inclusion and cross-border interventions (DLS, n.d. and University of St Andrews, 2024). Public Health Scotland regularly releases surveillance information on clusters of drug related harms through RADAR alerts (Public Health Scotland, 2026). Scotland has also implemented public health drug-checking facilities in Glasgow, allowing individuals to anonymously submit samples for testing to identify dangerous substances like nitazenes, with further point-of-care facilities planned in Edinburgh, Aberdeen, and Dundee (Scottish Government, 2025b). The *Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science* at the University of Dundee is also advancing detection of emerging psychoactive substances to support harm reduction and supply control (University of Dundee, 2025).

- **Lived and living experience (LLE) and community-driven innovation:** Lived and living experience is embedded across the system, as reflected in the *Health and Social Care Alliance Scotland's National Collaborative Roadmap* (Health and Social Care Alliance, 2022). Co-design and co-production approaches are widely adopted, while *Drug Research Network Scotland* (DRNS, n.d.) promotes the integration of lived experience and evidence into service design.

Scotland's Innovation Assets - Insights from the National Workshop

The greatest asset in Scotland's addiction care system is arguably its people. Community leaders, policy makers, researchers, participatory designers, founders, and funders collectively contribute to the development of invaluable addiction care products, services, practices, and infrastructure. On 27 April 2026, the IDEAS Hub invited these stakeholders to a policy workshop, titled *Collaborative Innovation in Scottish Addiction Care*. During the workshop, participants surfaced both the breadth and depth of existing pockets of excellence and assets across Scotland's innovation ecosystem. They also identified the need to better connect and integrate these assets within a more coordinated system to enable greater impact, including enhanced economic and societal value.

Community, lived experience, and third sector assets: The workshop reiterated that Scotland benefits from the tireless work of third sector organisations at a community level. Notable examples include *Simon Community Scotland* (2025), which provides intersectional, trauma-informed harm reduction services aligned with their homelessness mission. Alongside these, structured peer-support programmes such as *SMART Recovery UK* (n.d.) provide accessible, community-based support for individuals at different stages of recovery. Evidence from intervention studies, such as the *Supporting Harm Reduction through Peer Support* (SHARPS) (Parkes et. al, 2019), further highlights the potential of structured, peer-informed approaches to strengthen recovery pathways, complementing the work of community organisations. The *Scottish*

Drugs Forum (2026) is considered a leading voice in policy and advocacy, with a strong focus on reducing stigma through the inclusion and leadership of people with lived and living experience.

Academic, research, and innovation assets:

Scotland’s universities and research centres support innovation in addiction care, combining internationally recognised expertise with strong global networks. These span public health, medicine, social science, data science, economics and entrepreneurship, enabling Scotland to both contribute to and learn from international research and practice. Interdisciplinary centres and innovation hubs, increasingly bridge academia, policy, service delivery, and commercialisation, supporting real-world experimentation, evaluation, system learning, and pathways to development, adoption, and scale (Scottish Enterprise, 2025).

Clinical and service delivery assets: These assets deliver frontline pharmaceutical interventions that mitigate withdrawal symptoms (such as Buvidal² in custody) and reverse overdoses (such as take-home Naloxone), alongside the country’s transition to electronic prescribing. Integrated community-based services, such as the *Near Fatal Overdose Pathway* (NFOD) (See **Box 1**), further demonstrate progress in connecting care pathways and improving outcomes.

Digital data and infrastructure assets: As outlined in the previous section, Scotland has excellent digital data and infrastructure that can be leveraged in addiction care. These include *DHI’s R&D Data Exchange* which demonstrates the use of digital solutions in community-based interventions, as well as *Public Health Scotland’s Substance Use and Health Intelligence Linked Dataset* (SHleLD, n.d.), which uses administrative data to better understand populations at high risk of drug-related harm (Public Health Scotland, n.d.). *Research Data Scotland* enables linkage of data on individuals with addiction issues to wider social and household contexts, supporting research into pathways into and out of addiction and informing prevention strategies.

Policy, regulatory, and funding assets: Workshop participants highlighted Scotland’s *National Mission on Drug Deaths* as a widely recognised policy framework, alongside the *Medication Assisted Treatment* (MAT) standards, which guide clinical practice and

Box 1. Successful example of innovation in Scotland: Scottish Ambulance Service and NFOD

The Scottish Ambulance Service (SAS) near-fatal overdose (NFOD) pathway is an example of an innovation that has reached scale with measurable outcomes. It is an automated system which flags suspected overdoses from electronic patient records and triggers assertive outreach by the respective health boards. It responds to more than 7,000 incidents per year with an 83% engagement rate (University of St Andrews, 2026).

The NFOD pathway has a combination of features that make it a stand-out innovation. There is clear clinical ownership, automated infrastructure that works alongside individual goodwill, interoperability between NHS systems, and a defined handover mechanism.

² Buvidal is a medication used to treat opioid dependency.

service delivery. The £5 million *Reducing Drug Deaths Innovation Challenge* launched in 2023 by the Scottish Government’s Chief Scientist Office (CSO) and Office for Life Sciences (OLS) (UK Government, 2023), with clinical leadership provided by IDEAS Hub Co-Director Professor Baldacchino and managed by NHS Fife, supported entrepreneurs to develop innovative solutions to reduce drug-related harms (Health Innovation South East Scotland, 2023; University of St Andrews, 2025). More recently, Innovate UK – the national innovation agency supporting business-led innovation - launched the £20 million *Catalysing Innovation Awards* to support the development of innovations addressing drug and alcohol addiction challenges (Department of Health and Social Care, 2026) which will undoubtedly attract interest from Scotland.

Bottlenecks and System Challenges

While Scotland’s addiction care system has strong foundations, the *Collaborative Innovation in Scottish Addiction Care* policy workshop also highlighted a set of complex and entrenched challenges which limit the system’s ability to use its innovation assets and resources effectively, including:

- **High levels of stigma:** This remains a significant barrier, with a persistent culture of blame discouraging progress and limiting space for innovation. People experiencing addiction are often excluded from policy discussions, reinforcing self-stigma, while political narratives can inadvertently prioritise short-term interventions over long-term, system-level solutions.
- **Data issues:** Administrative data is not consistently shared between agencies, making it difficult to join up services and develop a comprehensive evidence base for addiction care. Aging information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructures within the NHS, alongside fragmented systems in social care, exacerbate this issue.
- **Pilot to service implementation issues:** Innovations remain trapped at the pilot stage because the transition is unsupported by the system or inconsistently resourced. Funding cycles, accountability structures, and commissioning models frequently stall at the point of embedding, limiting opportunities for scaling innovation.
- **Lack of connected ecosystem infrastructure:** Projects and initiatives remain siloed, with limited visibility across the system. This leads to variation in provision, reduced scale, and progress driven by individual rather than institutional coordination. It also contributes to institutional amnesia, where learning from past initiatives is not systematically captured or shared, resulting in duplication of effort. Establishing a shared mechanism to capture and disseminate “what works” would strengthen system memory and support wider adoption and scaling of effective innovations supported by sustained investment.
- **Workforce pressure and innovation fatigue:** The system is under sustained strain, resulting in capacity constraints. Cultural factors, including resistance to change, risk aversion and innovation fatigue, make it difficult to activate new

incentives in the system, with staff often constrained by their own organisational environment and structures.

- **Political issues:** Frequent policy changes and government turnover can lead to short-term funding cycles and uncertainty, discouraging entrepreneurs, investors and other stakeholders. Workshop participants highlighted the importance of sustained political commitment to support long-term prevention, recovery, and harm-reduction.

While these challenges impact different areas within the system, the workshop highlighted their interconnected nature. The complexity and interdependence of these issues represent a systemic bottleneck, underscoring the need for coordinated, system-wide responses.

Scotland's Global Opportunity - Strategic Levers for System Transformation

Despite these challenges, Scotland has a significant opportunity to build on what is working well and is globally distinctive. Four key system levers for transformation emerged from the workshop and podcast (see also **Figure 1**):

- **Build on the country's world-leading rights-based, risk-reduction approach:** There is strong consensus around the success of the Medication Assisted Treatment (MAT) Standards, the meaningful inclusion of lived and living experience, widespread and accessible Naloxone provision, and the establishment of the UK's first safer drug consumption facility. These approaches now require further embedding and scaling.
- **Act as a real-world innovation testbed:** Scotland provides a strong testbed for global innovation. It is of a scale that enables meaningful engagement across a wide range of stakeholders, while also allowing sufficiently robust evaluation of interventions, including among smaller populations with distinctive needs. Access to linked administrative data at a national level further supports testing, evaluation, and de-risking of innovation.
- **Adopt an innovation ecosystem approach:** Scotland has a strong appetite for innovation and entrepreneurship, providing a clear foundation for strong competitive advantage. However, activity remains fragmented across projects, data systems, stakeholders, and infrastructure. Strengthening and joining up these connections is essential to unlock system-wide impact and to enable innovations to be shared, connected and scaled, thereby reducing siloed learning and duplication of effort, and unlocking opportunities for wider adoption and sustained investment.
- **Leverage the IDEAS Hub:** Building on existing capacity while harnessing collective expertise and learning within the system, the IDEAS Hub can provide a critical national platform for research, innovation, education, and convening - driving systems thinking and facilitating innovation in addiction care in Scotland (Baldacchino, et al., 2026). The IDEAS Hub can also provide a global interface,

connecting Scotland’s assets and expertise with international networks in addiction, public health, and systems innovation to amplify learning, collaboration, and impact.

Figure 1. Scotland as a real-world testbed for innovation in addiction care

Taken together, these levers provide a framework for transforming Scotland’s existing strengths into coordinated, system-wide impact.

Conclusion

This report captures the current state of innovation in addiction care and demonstrates that Scotland is an entrepreneurial nation, with a wealth of activity flourishing across the country. These activities are driven by committed individuals and organisations, and underpinned by a mission-oriented, rights-based approach to policy and practice. Scotland possesses a strong and distinctive set of innovation assets; the opportunity now is to configure these more intentionally to reduce fragmentation and duplication, maximise impact, and power the next generation of innovation.

This report provides the foundation for a national call to action: to develop a coherent, system-level framework for innovation; to create a sustained space for knowledge exchange and collaboration; and to assert Scotland as a global leader in addiction care innovation. The IDEAS Hub is well positioned to play a central convening role in enabling this to happen.

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Please cite as: Mitka, M., Petzinger, J., Schofield, J., Mackenzie, M., Dyson, S., Romenska, S., Halliday, R., Donnelly, P., & Baldacchino, A. (2026). State of Addiction Care Innovation in Scotland. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20431496>